

The history of Shahrissabz city neighborhood assemblies during the years of independence.

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Annotation: In this article, the activities of the existing 40 neighborhood chairmen and deputies, the evaluation of the effectiveness of the work of the employees and activists of the citizens' assemblies, the results of the evaluation of the effectiveness of the employees and activists of the citizens' assemblies were reviewed.

Key words: Citizens' gatherings, "Kulolchilik", "Zargarli", "Koshhovuz", "Kaziguzar", Spiritual and educational issues, law enforcement, business issues, exemplary, higher, secondary special.

Today, Shahrissabz city operates 40 neighborhoods. It should be noted that not all community assemblies are functioning at an exemplary [2:1492-1495] level. By the end of 2019, on the basis of the regulation approved by the statement No. 2 of the Republican Council for the Coordination of the Activities of Citizens' Self-Government Bodies dated July 18, 2017 "On Measures for Rating the Performance of Citizens' Assemblies' Employees and Activists"[3:135-138] The results of the evaluation of the efficiency of the work of the employees and activists of citizens' meetings [4:1-6] were as follows: Shahrissabz cities "Sinabog", "Faizabad", "Buston" MFY activities (71-100 points) were recognized as "exemplary". Activities of "Choshtepa" MFY (51-70 points), "good", "Orda", "Zingaron", "Pottery", "Zargarlik", "Koshkhovuz", "Kaziguzar", "Ziyokor", "K.Bakhshi", "Kunchiqar", "Kushkhana", "Uychilik", "Noozgo", "Aksaroy", "Khabarlik", "Navroz", "Sariosiyo", "Galaba", "Silk Road", "Bunyodkor", "Kesh", "Dostlik", "Turon", "Pillakashlik", "Tutzor", "Kamalat", "Boghibahor", "Teparlik", "Marifat", "Yangi Hayot", "Korasuv", "Yashil Dayar", "K.Novat", "Ammoghan", "Namaton", "Guliston", "Uyamovut" MFY activities (up to 50 points) were evaluated as "average"[1].

The age and education of the chairpersons of Shahrissabz city citizens' meetings [5:96-100] were as follows. Out of 40 existing MFY chairmen, 4 were women, 4 were 30-40 years old, 19 (4) were 50-60 years old, and 2 were over 60 years old. The education of the chairpersons is 33 with higher education, 7 with secondary education.

The age and education of the secretaries in charge of the Shahrissabz City Citizens' Meeting [6:121-123] are as follows: 40 MFY (34) women, 3(3) under 30 years old, 8(2) 30-40-year-olds, 40-50-year-olds 25(23), 50-60-year-olds 4(2), according to the

information of responsible secretaries, 2 with higher education, 38 with secondary special education.

The age and education of the deputy chairman of Shahrissabz city citizens' meetings - advisers on youth issues [7:128-131] were as follows. 13 out of 40 MFY are women, 23(3) under 30, 7(4) 30-40-year-olds, 7(5) 40-50-year-olds, 3(1) 50-60-year-olds, and 20 with higher education. 20 with secondary education.

The age and education of the deputy chairman of Shahrissabz City Citizens' Meetings - Elderly and Veterans [8:128-132] affairs were as follows. 6 out of 40 MFY are women, 40-50 years old, 1 woman, 50-60 years old, 30(5), 25 have higher education, 15 have secondary specialized education.

The age and education of the advisers on spiritual and educational issues[9:73-76] were as follows. 40(15), 1 under 30, 4(2) 30-40-year-olds, 14(6) 40-50-year-olds, 10(5) 50-60-year-olds, 11(3) over 60, according to education, 26 higher [10], 14 with secondary special education.

The age and education of the advisers of Shahrissabz city on entrepreneurship, assistance to the activities of estate landowners and improvement works [11:59-63] were as follows. 40 (17 women), 7(3) under 30, 16(7) 30-40-year-olds, 8(4) 40-50-year-olds, 6(3) 50-60-year-olds, 2(1) over 60) made [12:86-90], 20 with higher education, 16 with secondary special education.

As of January 1, 2022, there are 40 MFY in Shahrissabz city, 28 with a population of 1,000-2,000 [13:386-391], 9 with a population of 2,000-4,000, and 3 with a population of 4,000-6,000. In terms of the number of families, the number of families up to 1000 is 30 MFY, and the number of families from 1000 to 2000 is 10. There are 37 MFYs with a household size of up to 1,000 and 3 MFYs with a household size of 1,000 to 2,000.

There are 40 chairmen of citizens' meetings, 1 vacant chairmen of citizen's meetings [14:292-296], 39 (8) active chairmen of citizen's meetings, 4(2) from 35 to 45 years old, 19(1) from 45 to 55 years old.), 16(5) over 55 years old, 16(7) retired chairmen, including 2 military service pensioners, 31 with higher education, 8 with secondary specialized education.

17 people under the age of 30, 19 30-40-year-olds, 4 40-60-year-olds, and according to their education, 40 have higher education.

There are 4 deputy heads of citizens' meetings for family, women's and social and spiritual issues, 4 from 30 to 40 years old, 32 from 40 to 60 years old, 4 over 60 years old, 16 with higher education, and 24 with secondary specialized education.

32 out of 40 deputies of the chairman of citizens' meetings on improvement, real estate and business issues are women, 1 under 30 years old, 10 under 30-40 years old, 29 between 40 and 60 years old, according to education, 12 have higher education, 26 have secondary education. special education. The number of deputy chairmen who resigned in 2022 was 1 person.

All-round development of the activities of citizens' self-government bodies, ensuring the stability of the social and spiritual environment in their neighborhoods [15:26-28], raising the political consciousness and thinking of citizens, working with young people and women, helping them to find work, helping the needy segments of the population In order to further improve the work carried out in areas such as support, work is being continued rapidly.

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